

TSHE RING MTSHO'S (B. 1920) FLIGHT FROM MGO LOG (GUOLUO) IN THE 1930S

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ABSTRACT

Tshe ring mtsho (b. 1920) was thirteen years old in what is today's Mgo log (Guoluo) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province when she was forced to flee because of an invasion by a Muslim warlord. After walking nearly one thousand kilometers, Tshe ring mtsho eventually reached Zho 'ong (Shuangpeng) Village, Rma lho (Huangnan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon, married, and had a son.

KEYWORDS

Golok women lives, Ma family, Mgo log, Tibetan women's lives, Qinghai history

INTRODUCTION

Tshe ring mtsho was born in the modern-day Mgo log (Guoluo) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China in 1920.¹ Ma Qi (1869-1931) and Ma Lin² (1873-1945), members of a prominent Muslim Ma family in northwest China, exercised violent control over the inhabitants. They destroyed numerous Buddhist monasteries and carried out seven genocidal expeditions into the Mgo log region, killing thousands of Tibetans (Uradyn:2002).

I, Pad ma don grub (1994), from Zho 'ong (Shuangpeng) Village Reb gong (Tongren) County, Rma lho (Huangnan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China, interviewed Tshe ring mtsho in the summer holidays of 2015 and 2017 in Zho 'ong Village. I did not record the conversation, nor did I take photos and notes because I did not want to upset Tshe ring mtsho. Once I was back home, I immediately wrote out what she had told me.

Tshe ring mtsho was reluctant to mention people who had passed away the first time we spoke, but she told me more after visiting her three times in 2017.

The sky was clear, there was a gentle breeze, and birds were chirping in trees one summer afternoon in 2017. Tshe ring mtsho was ninety-seven. I walked through the small village where she lived. A little boy took twenty RMB from her, his great-grandmother, and raced off to school. Suddenly, Tshe ring mtsho shouted, "Give me that money, or I'll tell your father! He'll punish you!"

I had last seen her in 2015. She had noticeably aged and now walked with a cane, was bent at the waist, used one hand to thump her waist from time to time, and had a persistent cough. She had more wrinkles and more white hair, which was short and resembled a layer of frost. Her large eyes were deeply sunken.

She did not want her nine-year-old great-grandson to be punished. Tshe ring mtsho had intended to give him two RMB of pocket money but had mistakenly given him twenty RMB. After

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¹ Traditional Tibetans are aware of the zodiac year of their birth. She was born in the Year of the Monkey in 1920.

² Ma Qi and Ma Lin were brothers and sent troops to suppress Tibetans in Mgo log where they established a garrison in the 1921-1935 period (Danzhu Angben 2003:496).

explaining to the boy why she wanted him to return the twenty RMB, he ignored her and ran off. Tshe ring mtsho sat on her house doorstep, her prayer beads in her right hand, and chanted *oM ma Ni pad+me hU~M*.³

When I got near her, she slowly approached me, thinking that I was her great-grandson. I cautiously greeted, "How have you been?"

"I'm fine. Who are you?" she gently inquired.

"I'm Sgrol ma's son," I answered.

She gasped, "Oh! Sgrol ma?"

"Yes! Do you remember you lived in the tent next to my mother's many years ago? "

She then recognized me. I had visited her two years earlier after my mother had often mentioned that Tshe ring mtsho had many stories. My impression was that she was a very strong, brave woman.

"Why did you come to see me? Did your mother tell you to come?" Tshe ring mtsho asked.

"No, but she told me about you. Today, I came to see how you were doing and also to hear your stories," I said.

Tshe ring mtsho said, "What can an old woman who has never been to school tell you? I can't even properly organize my thoughts these days."

"Please just tell whatever you remember about the past," I encouraged.

She invited me to her large house in a courtyard with a pear tree in the middle of a garden. Tshe ring mtsho enjoyed raising zinnias, lilacs, red peonies, and roses, which were in bright, colorful bloom. The wood house featured window frames and architraves artistically carved into the shapes of the Eight Auspicious Symbols.⁴ I helped her bring two chairs to the sunny balcony, where we sat.

"If you really want me to tell my story, you'll probably want to know where I was born, about my childhood, and the suffering we experienced. But, frankly speaking, I don't want to talk about such things."

"Why?" I asked.

"Many people have passed away. I will be sad to mention their names."

I felt uncomfortable encouraging her to talk about the past, but she continued:

My name is Tshe ring mtsho. I am from Mgo log, in the mountain range of noble A myes rma chen,⁵ whose snow-capped peak I could see on a clear day. I was born in A skyong gong ma.⁶ More than seventy years have passed since I fled my native hometown. I am an old woman now.

It was a wonderful time of life in A skyong gong ma 'Joyous Grassland' that was as rich and beautiful as a heavenly palace and full of people, wealth, and brilliant wildflower blossoms. My parents herded, and we lived a prosperous life. All tribal families shared a grassland for herding for a few short months before the families moved to other pastures. The tents were far from each other, and it was not easy to communicate with each other.

I had two brothers and a younger sister. My mother told me that I was born in the Year of the Monkey. My older brother was seven years older than me, and my elder brother was five years older. When my parents went up the mountains to herd, my brothers stayed at home to care for my sister, who was two

³ The six-syllable mantra of Avalokiteśvara.

⁴ "The eight auspicious Buddhist symbols (Tib. bkra shis rtags bryad) consist of: a parasol, a pair of golden fishes, a treasure vase, a lotus, a white right-spiraling conch shell, an endless knot, a banner of victory, and a golden wheel. Originally these formed a grouping of early Indian symbols of royalty which were presented at such ceremonies as the investiture or coronation of a king" (Beer 1999:171).

⁵ A much-visited pilgrim site that many A mdo Tibetans refer to as the soul mountain of snowy Tibet.

⁶ Today's A skyong gong ma (Shang gongma) Township, Dga' bde (Gande) County, Mgo log Prefecture.

years younger than me, and me. Because she was the youngest child, my family loved her very much. Our family lived very happily.

Unfortunately, when she began to walk and talk, she became ill, and her condition worsened. We could only consult *bla ma* and *sngags pa* 'lay tantric practitioners' for medical treatment. My father took her on horseback to find a Tantric practitioner who knew medicine. He gave them some Tibetan medicine, they returned home, and my sister began to improve.

Very soon, from what I heard, more than 7,000 people were killed in one day in the whole region. That day was the most painful experience of my life. I saw corpses of old people and children everywhere. Many of the monasteries were destroyed, along with Buddhist scriptures and Buddha images. The situation got worse, with many women and children detained. Young, beautiful women were raped, and older men were violently beaten and insulted. More taxes were levied. This situation caused many to flee without any food. Many died from hunger and cold as they escaped.

It was a dark day in the spring of The Year of the Sheep (1933). The mountains were still covered with snow, and the grass had pushed up from the earth. The glaciers were melting. One night, Ma Lin sent his troops to search A skyong gong ma brutally. He arrested all the men in our tribe and beat and interrogated them to learn more about those opposing him. Women were shut in a cowshed.

My mother cleverly hid us under a pile of dry yak dung in a place where the yaks were kept. They searched our tent for a long time, looking for our coral necklaces, gold and silver rings, and other ornaments, but they did not find us. To prevent them from searching, my mother presented herself, and the soldiers left with her. Late in the morning, she was released and had suffered because she lacked spirit, and bruises covered her face.

From what my mother said, the soldiers had killed many women because they had opposed the enemy. It was like a dark dream. We began our escape. On the way, when we made a fire and tried to heat water, we heard the sounds of gunfire before the water boiled. Soldiers were chasing people, so we could not eat anything hot during the day and only heat water at night. We scrimped and saved food because we could not carry much with us.

We lived like wild animals. While escaping, some people hid beneath a glacier to escape from soldiers who shot at the glacier. Some were injured, and some died. After the hateful soldiers had left, I repeatedly shouted for my mother, brothers, and sister, but they did not respond, so I fled with an older woman who was ill.

After almost four months of flight, we were out of Mgo log, and the soldiers stopped pursuing us. We did not have enough food. We followed a very long mountain range for many days and then came to a vast grassland. It was as beautiful as our previous hometown. Various wild animals lived there. Fortunately, we were able to dig *gro ma*¹ 'wild yams' for something to eat.

When I reached Zho 'ong Village, I was thirteen-years-old and immediately began to work for others. When I was eighteen, I married a kind man in Zho 'ong Village, where about 150 families lived, nestled in the mountains. Our home was in the middle of the village with two courtyards. One courtyard had a garden where we grew flowers. From the roof of the house, we could see mountains and forests.

There were several rooms in the house yard. My husband and I shared a bedroom and ate in the adjacent kitchen. The stove there kept us warm, especially during winter. The house also had a big guest room. The rooms were connected and had doors out to the courtyard. We kept livestock in a big room in one courtyard.

We cultivated wheat, broad beans, barley, oats, and potatoes, which grew very well. People didn't know how to grow much else. No one left the village to work outside. Our breakfast was *rtsam pa* with milk tea. Lunch and supper were noodles. Sometimes, we also ate mutton and beef.

¹ *Potentilla anserina* L, 'wild yams'.

My husband herded sheep, and my son helped me cook and tend the fields. We had over one hundred sheep and a few milk yaks. We were among the most prosperous village families. We lived a happy life.

In 1949, when my son was just six-years-old, my husband became seriously ill and lay in bed for a few months, hardly eating at all. There were no doctors or hospitals. Death was a constant worry. My husband died and, a few years later, my mother-in-law also passed away. My life was then incredibly difficult.

Several village men wanted to marry me, Some people advised me to remarry, but I did not. I was not yet thirty, and I could have remarried, but for the sake of my son and my true love for my dead husband, I refused. As a result, I was teased and insulted in the village, but my son gave me the courage to get through the hard times. I put all my hopes in him.

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TIBETAN TERMS

a mdo ཨ་མདོ།
 a myes rma chen ཨ་མྱེས་རྩ་ཚེན།
 a skyong gong ma ཨ་སྐྱོང་གོང་མ།
 Avalokiteśvara, spyan ras gzigs ལྷན་རས་གཟིགས།
 bkra shis rtags brgyad བཀ་ཤིས་རྟགས་བརྒྱད།
 bla ma ལྷ་མ།
 dga' bde དགའ་བདེ།
 gro ma ལྷོ་མ།
 mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།
 oM ma Ni pad+me hU~M ཨོཾ་མཎི་པདྨེ་ཧཱུྃ།
 Pad ma don grub པད་མ་དོན་གྲུབ།
 reb gong རེབ་གོང།
 rma lho རྩ་ལྷོ།
 rtsam pa རུམ་པ།
 sgrol ma སྐྱོལ་མ།
 sngags pa སྐྱགས་པ།
 tshe ring mtsho ཚེ་རིང་མཚོ།
 zho 'ong ཞོ་འོང།

CHINESE TERMS

Avalokiteśvara, Guan shiyin pusa 观世音菩萨
 Gande 甘德
 Guoluo 果洛
 Huangnan 黄南
 Ma Bufang 马步芳
 Ma Lin 马麟
 Ma Qi 马麒
 Minzu 民族
 Qinghai 青海
 RMB 人民币
 Shang gongma 上贡麻
 Shuangpeng 双朋
 Tongren 同仁
 Wanmadongzhi 完么东智